

Comparative Analysis of Advertising Strategies and Consumer Preferences: A Study of Complan and Horlicks in the Nutritional Supplement Market

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Abstract

"Advertising strategies are crucial in the modern landscape of business competition. They serve to draw the attention of potential customers towards a business, its products, or services. Through advertising, customers are informed about the different brands present in the market and the range of products that could be beneficial to them. The strength of a brand is often directly linked to the effectiveness of its advertising strategies. Indeed, nearly every business globally engages in advertising at some stage."

Keywords: Advertising strategies, Complan and Horlicks, Nutritional supplement, Market.

Introduction

As far as concern of advertising strategies of Complan milk powder and Horlicks milk powder both are powerful brands and keep high marketing shares as well maintaining good sales. As we know that in advertising strategy brand is a powerful tool for positioning your product. Complan milk powder is the product of Heinz and Horlicks milk powder is the product of GlaxoSmithKline. Both companies are strong competitor of each other.

Advertising stands as a key medium of communication between organizations and their customers. It plays a crucial role in informing consumers about various aspects of products and services. Functioning as a marketing tool, advertising informs consumers about the range of brands and products available in the market, and their potential usefulness. Additionally, it aims to influence customer behavior, either by encouraging the continuation of current behavior or by persuading them to adopt new actions regarding a product. The primary objective often revolves around shaping consumer behavior towards a particular commercial offering, highlighting the features and benefits of products to transform potential customers into actual consumers. Beyond customer engagement, advertising can also serve an internal purpose by reinforcing the company's stability and success to employees and shareholders.

Complan and Horlicks are milk-based nutritional supplements produced by two multinational corporations. The Horlicks brand has its origins with two British brothers, William and James Horlick, who after emigrating to America, established J&W Horlicks in Chicago in 1873. Now over 138 years old, Horlicks has become a beloved beverage with a rich history, including its significant role during the 1948 Olympic Games in London, where it was provided at various venues to energize athletes

List of competitors is given below:

- Horliks
 - Bournvita
 - Hi-Complan
 - Complan
 - Boost
 - Milo
 - To determine the perception of the consumer about the advertising of Horlicks milk powder.
 - To determine the perception of the consumer about the advertising of Complan milk powder.
 - To compare the advertising strategies of the selected brands from the consumer point of views.
- This research will be very helpful for the Complan and Horlicks to improve their advertising strategies as both brands are most power brands and strong competitors of each other. This research will help me to find how these companies registered their messages in the mind of consumer with the help of advertising. In a successful business advertising play a vital role .Advertising does not means selling of products it helps in increasing the sales of product. This research will be helpful to find which product is preferred by the consumers most. This research is providing me opportunity to conduct research and will be very helpful for me to check the quality of the products and analyze both products.

Table 1 Analysis/comparison of product strategies

Sr.	Horliks	Complan
1	It was first patented the malt based milked dranked as baby food.	Complan proclaims itself as Complan for Growth.
2	It is a substitute of milk as Baby food.	Tagline of its brands is “a complete planned food and ideal for growing children.
3	From a drink that was supposed to promote a good nights sleep to one that can help children grow taller stronger and sharper.	Complan has protein content which is the best for the growth of children.
4	It’s a brand Image of GSK.	It’s a brand image of Heniz
5	It’s a health drink recommended by doctors to something that is nurshing and enjoyable.	It is successful in translating its clams of being a nutrition drink
6	It was initial introduce both a substitute and and addictive to milk.	Its ideal for the Childs physical and mantel development.

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7	GSK positioned horlicks as pleasurable nutrition by launching it in vanilla, chocolate and honey flavors.	It is specifically designed to provide balanced nourishment
8	It introduced other variants like jr horlicks women horlicks mother horlicks and horlicks lite to reposition itself from the children segments to other segments for consumption.	It provides 26 vitamins and minerals for health and vitality
9	GSK launched Chill Milk an instant milkshake in the dairy based product in the market.	It helps to improve stamina and immune system of your body.
10	The brand today talks to every one of the family.	Helps in resistance power.
11	The brand strengthens its market position with the power of advertisement and distribution network.	It contains calcium for healthy bones
12	The idea of horlicks is to address all age groups.	Its balanced goodness contains everything your body needs to recover fast from illness.

- It provides nutrition to body for growing up.
- It helps to maintain your body health.
- It improves your stamina and helps children growing up in a healthier way.
- It supports mental & physical development.

It is mainly a substitute of the milk for the children and it improves the body health of the consumer.

The marketing mix is a promotion tool as well as a business tool used in marketing. There are four P's of marketing mix that is product price place and promotion. Where is

Complan is one of the leading suppliers of the Dairy Products. Complan engaged in offering a wide variety of energy Health Drinks, which are high in nutritional values including proteins and vitamins. These are suitable for providing more energy and are liked by people of all age groups.

In the past few years, Complan has added millions of customers in Pakistan. Complan is using many print media, billboards and electronic media for making awareness of their products among the different users all over Pakistan. Complan is extensively promoting its products to the general public. Complan has offering different products for different customers according to the age, sex and gender.

Complan mainly targets growing children because children need adequate and balanced nutrition to help them achieve their maximum growth potential. Complan with 26 vital nutrients in planned proportions is the ideal food supplement for the children during these crucial years. Complan provides half your daily allowance of vitamins C and E as well as being an important source of iron and calcium. Other than children they also target other persons like Active people, which needs the extra nourishment for traveling & sporting activities. Busy Executives, who now & then have to skip their meal due to increased work load. Pregnant Women & Lactating Mothers because they require nutrients during these vital periods. Complan has targeted all age groups because it provides nutrients and energy which is very vital for every person. Complan is recommended by doctors and healthcare professionals.

Table 2: Comparison of product strategies

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Sr.	Horlicks	Complan
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4	It’s a brand Image of GSK.	It’s a brand image of Heniz
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Complan has been successful in the translating that it is complete nutritional drink for the growth of the consumer. Complan has entered in the market through the doctors. Doctors recommend complan for the growth and healthy bones. It contains 26vital Nutrients which are vital for the growth and healthy bones. In order to expand the use of product it introduced different flavors in the market.

As we know that it is introduced in Pak at 2010. Now in Pakistan its sale turn over about 20 million

in last two years. In the present era there are many competitors of Complan and they attract the customers on their side. That is the maturity stage where different competitors enter in the market. Complan is now on the maturity stage.

The elements in the packaging of Complan are given below:

- Its packaging shows taller and strong children.
- It indicates the happy and active life.
- The orange colour of the packaging is very attractive and denotes fitness.
- In the packaging the child shows the growth and health.

Literature Review

Advertising serves as a crucial link between organizations and their customers. It plays a vital role in informing customers about various products and services. Essentially, advertising is a marketing communication tool that introduces consumers to different brands and a diverse range of products that may be beneficial to them. Its purpose extends beyond just informing; it aims to persuade or influence the audience to either maintain their loyalty or to try new products. Primarily, the goal of advertising is to shape consumer behavior towards a specific commercial offering, highlighting the features and benefits of products and turning potential customers into actual consumers. Another important aspect of advertising is to bolster the confidence of employees or stakeholders in the company's success and viability.

Taking the example of Complan and Horlicks, two renowned milk powder brands from multinational companies, we can see the impact of advertising. Horlicks, a brand with a rich 138-year history, was founded by British brothers William and James Horlick. After moving to America, they established the company J&W Horlicks in Chicago in 1873. Horlicks gained fame for its extensive use during the 1948 Olympic Games in London, where it was made available to athletes across all venues for an energy boost. In Pakistan, Horlicks is produced and marketed by GlaxoSmithKline.

Complan, on the other hand, was launched by Glaxo in 1954. Initially part of Glaxo's Farley Health Product subsidiary, the Complan UK brand was sold to Boots in 1988. In India, Complan stayed with Glaxo until 1994, when it was acquired by Heinz, who also took over the UK brand that year. In Pakistan, Complan has been marketed by Heinz since 2010.

The competitive battle between Complan and Horlicks began in the 1960s and has been ongoing. Over time, both brands have engaged in intense comparative advertising across print and television, focusing on factors like ingredients, protein content, growth potential, and flavor variety. However, in late 2008, the competition escalated when both GlaxoSmithKline Consumer Healthcare (makers of Horlicks) and Heinz India (makers of Complan) released advertisements directly comparing their products using the competitor's trademarks. This aggressive advertising approach led industry observers to comment that both companies were denigrating each other's brand. Generally, disputes over disparaging advertisements are settled by the Advertising Standards Council of India, but the continuous exchange of barbs led the companies to seek legal resolution. In September 2008, Heinz approached the Bombay High Court over a Horlicks advertisement, and in December 2008, GSK filed a case in the Delhi High Court against a Complan advertisement.

This ongoing conflict between GSK and Heinz highlights the complexities and challenges of

comparative advertising, including the legal and ethical considerations. This case provides an opportunity for students to analyze the advertising strategies of Complan and Horlicks over the years, understand the challenges of comparative advertising, assess its effectiveness in boosting brand image and sales, explore the consequences of the advertising war between the two brands, and discuss the legal and ethical issues involved.

Theoretical framework

H1 Consumer perception comparative analysis of tv advertisement of horlicks and complain is not possible.

Methodology

Primary source of the data collection is the original information which is directly come from the consumer its may be doctors, teachers, shopkeepers, athlete, customer and family members because they consume powder milk in daily life and can give good feedback. Further more the official representatives and as well as employees of the companies may be the primary source.

Secondary source of data collection are the information that is originally presented elsewhere. It is also called indirect source of data collection. I collected my data from the secondary source from the official websites of Complan and Horlicks. Companies publishes all the information regarding company in their websites which is correct and it is secondary source.

And I have collected my data from the primary source from the employees of the company and the others. Primary and secondary sources of data collection are relative terms, and some sources may be classified as primary or secondary it depends on how it is used.

We have used and design the structured questionnaire format in order to collect the data for this project. This technique of data collection is very helpful to achieve the objectives. I have develop structured questionnaire format according to ones objectives by using scales and values.

Sampling is concerned with the selection of a subset of individuals from within a statistical population to estimate characteristics of the whole population. It is a small set of population which represent the whole population. In this project the target population is general public because everyone consumes milk on daily basis. Two advantages of sampling are that the cost is lower and the data collection is faster. We have drawn a sample of 200 customers and designed a questionnaire for the purpose of primary data collection and all this process is genuine because I have been doing

it by myself and collected the data that is 100 % genuine. I have used convenience sampling technique for the data collection.

Data Analysis

Cumulative Percent	Valid Percent	Percent	Frequency	Valid
13.0	13.0	13.0	26	Inter
60.0	47.0	47.0	94	Graduate
100.0	40.0	40.0	80	Masters
	100.0	100.0	200	Total

Table 3: Qualification

200	Valid	N
0	Missing	

The cumulative percentage of inter is 13.0 valid percentage also 13.0 and total percentage is also 13.0 frequency is 26. The cumulative percentage of graduates is 60.0 valid percentage is 47.0 and total percentage is 47.0 frequency is 94. In that analysis the master persons more the other.

Table 4: Gender

Cumulative Percent	Valid Percent	Percent	Frequency	Valid
35.0	35.0	35.0	70	Male
100.0	65.0	65.0	130	Female
	100.0	100.0	200	Total

In case of gender cumulative percentage 35.0 and valid percentage 35.0 total percentage 35.0 frequency is 70 for male. In case of gender female cumulative percentage is 100.0 and valid percentage is 65.0 total percentage is 65.0 frequency is 130. In this analysis we analysis that female is more consuming brand than male.

Table 5 Age

Cumulative Percent	Valid Percent	Percent	Frequency	Valid
3.0	3.0	3.0	6	Less than 18 years
55.5	52.5	52.5	105	18-25 years
92.5	37.0	37.0	74	25-30 years
100.0	7.5	7.5	15	Above 30 years
	100.0	100.0	200	Total

In case of age the cumulative percentage of less than 18 years is 3.0 and valid percentage is also 3.0 total percentage is same as above frequency is 6. 18-25 years cumulative percentage is 55.5 valid percentage is 52.5 total percentage 3.0 frequency 105. 25-30 years cumulative percentage is 92.5 valid percentage is 37.0 percentage is 3.0 and frequency is 74. Above then 30 years cumulative percentage is 100.0 valid percentage is 7.5 and percentage is 7.5 frequency is 15. In this analysis we observe that in age 18-25 years persons is more than others.

Discussion:

Advertising strategies play a very important role in today's age of business competition. Advertising is used to attract attention of prospective customers to a business or its products or services.

According to my project, I compared the advertising strategy of Complan and Horlicks. As far as concern of advertising strategies of Complan milk powder and Horlicks milk powder both are powerful brands and keep high marketing shares as well maintaining good sales.

Complan and Horlicks are milk powder of two multinational companies. Horlicks was founded by two British brothers, William and James Horlick. Horlicks is 138 years old. In Pakistan, Horlicks is produced and marketed by GlaxoSmithKline. In 2010, Complan was launched by Glaxo in 1954. In Pakistan, Complan is marketed by Heinz In 2010.

As we know that both companies are running well. Both companies are reputable and good market place. Basic concern of this project is to determine the perception of the consumer about the advertising of Horlicks milk powder and Complan milk powder and other object is also compare the advertising strategies of the selected brands from the consumer point of views.

With the help of this project both companies can improve their advertising strategies because both are competitors. It also shows that which company's product is preferred by consumer. This project is also showing the quality of the products and analyze both products.

Complan is a better growing brand in Pakistan. Consumer most aware about Complan as compare to Horlicks brand. Because of most of mass marketing of Complan in Pakistan. People know that product due to good mass marketing in Pakistan and its also popular in children they want to drink this shake as compare to Horlicks.

Conclusion:

According to objective which I conclude that Complan Sale is better than Horlicks in Pakistan. Complan advertising better than Horlicks in Pakistan. Complan has more loyal consumers and it has succeeded to attract new consumers. Complan has more emotional and sentimental which targets the children which is "Bayta agar hight brahany ki jaldi hai tu mami sy bolo Complan bhi Pilain." Complan is respected as a better health beverage than Horlicks. Other hand horlicks advertisement is not playing in Pakistan tv Channels. But Indian tv channels playing Horlicks commercial. Horlicks tv commercial is not very attractive they just say that "Stronger Taller Longer". Changes can attract new customers to use their product.

Recommendations:

There are some recommendations which we have to give in manner of this study. The advertising strategies of both companies have some deficiencies. Horlicks must focus the world market and advertise their product in Pakistan. The advertising strategies of Complan milk is effective because it frequently occurred on T.V. On other hand Horlicks advertising strategies of the product is not good and not frequently occurred on T.V. Such kind of emotional ads are needed to counter the Pakistani households where people are very much sensitive. Horlicks must focus all over the world.

Limitations:

To reduce my expense I also used secondary source of data. It is economical. It also saves efforts, expenses, and time. With the help of observation I conclude the results. With the help of Observation technique, we collect data and interpreted the results very carefully so that my project

shows accuracy.

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